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Availability And Utilization Of Instructional Materials For The Implementation Of Chemistry Curriculum In Senior Secondary Schools In North Central Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the availability and utilization of instructional materials in Chemistry Curriculum implementation by teachers in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria. The study employed descriptive survey research design. The population of the study was four thousand and ninety -six Chemistry teachers from the three selected states from the North Central zone. The sample size comprised of 264 Chemistry teachers who were randomly selected from using multistage sampling procedure. Availability and utilization of instructional materials was the instrument used for data collection. The reliability was determined by internal consistency method and Cronbach Alpha statistics which gave a reliability coefficient of 0.82 and this indicate the high reliability of the instrument. The data collected was analysed using frequency counts, percentage, mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while the null hypotheses were tested using independent t-test statistics at 0.05 level of significance. Findings of the study showed that there was no significant difference in the level of availability of instructional materials for the implementation of the Chemistry curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools based on location. There was significant difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum based on location, It was recommended among others that; School administrators should ensure close monitoring of Chemistry teachers for implementing the appropriate teaching methods in teaching Chemistry Curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools.

Keywords: Chemistry, Curriculum, Instructional materials, Availability, Utilization and teachers

INTRODUCTION

Science is the cornerstone of all technical advancement and the basis for a nation's progress. For a developing nation like Nigeria, to achieve a significant level of scientific and technological progress, the propagation of scientific knowledge and abilities must be a top priority. Science teaching in Nigeria commenced in form of nature study, which subsequently evolved into the teaching of general science. Subsequently, it was separated into three major disciplines of Biology, Chemistry, and Physics (FGN, 2013).

Chemistry in the content of the study is a sub discipline of science that deals with the study of matter and the substances that constitutes it. The successful implementation of Chemistry Curriculum may be influenced by various factors, including the proficiency of teachers, availability of instructional materials, adequacy of school infrastructure, pedagogical approaches among others.

In the realm of Chemistry education, educators are expected to employ diverse pedagogical approaches to facilitate the successful execution of the updated Curriculum, which may address the issue of suboptimal Curriculum implementation. In addition, conducting practical is an integral part of effective Chemistry instruction, the subject consists of many topics whose content demands experimental verification (Ijidike & Oyelana, 2015). Chepkorir, Cheptonui and Chemutai (2014) concur that for students to master chemical reactions, they need to mix the chemicals and observe subsequent reactions. Laboratory stock keeping records for none and consumable items should also be kept and updated regularly for accountability purposes. Mere provision of materials and facilities alone is insufficient to bring about improvement in student's achievement.

According to Ijidike and Oyelana (2015), shortage of laboratories contributes to ineffective Chemistry teaching in schools. To enhance the conduciveness of the laboratory for teaching and learning, the facility should have adequate water supply, a good power supply system, enough furniture, good ventilation, and a clean environment. The facility should be supplied with adequate stock of instructional materials such as chemicals, apparatus, operational equipment, charts and models.

According to Gatana (2011) inadequacy of chemical materials and apparatus in the laboratory contribute to low performance in Chemistry. The laboratory safety measures should also be in place through the supply of first aid kits, lab coats, gloves, In addition, gender is another factor to consider in Curriculum implementation. Gender is a set of characteristics distinguishing between male and female, it refers to the socially constructed roles, behaviour, activities and attributes that a particular society considers appropriate for men and women. Traditionally, gender stereotype has over the years continued to limit female's capabilities and constrain their ability to participate in all aspects of human endeavour. Gender issues themselves affect all aspects of the society to the extent that access of women to certain profession or competencies in higher institution is constrained by these same sex-role stereotypes. It has been argued that this long-standing gender bias also reflected in performance levels.

Location of schools could also be a factor that affects Chemistry Curriculum implementation. Location is a particular place in relation to other areas. School location refers to the part of the state where schools are sited. It could be in an urban area where essential amenities are present for use or in rural where essential amenities may not be present for use. The students in urban areas are more likely to be exposed to adequate teaching and learning materials for effective implementation of Chemistry Curriculum than their rural area counterparts.

Statement of the Problem

Chemistry serves as a mandatory requirement for admission into professions that are science- oriented pursuits, including but not limited to medicine, engineering, pharmacy, biotechnology, agriculture, and related fields, at the tertiary-levels of academic establishments. Despite the highlighted importance of Chemistry knowledge in the academic arena, the academic performance of students in West African Examination Council (WAEC) over the years has perpetually remained lower in comparison to its fellow science subjects namely biology and physics (WAEC 2018-2022).

The laboratory facilities in Nigerian secondary schools were inadequate for teaching Chemistry. Hence, there is still the need for improvement in the implementation process in order to reduce underachievement in Chemistry education, therefore, it is deemed necessary to assess the Chemistry Curriculum implementation. Implementation in this study is the extent at which teaching of Chemistry Curriculum content to secondary school students is achieved.

In South Africa, several factors influence the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum. These include inadequacy of; practical lessons, laboratory facilities and relevant textbooks. Others are; teacher unprofessionalism while on the job, inadequate attendance of teachers to in-service courses, workshops and seminars, lack of laboratory attendants or presence of unqualified ones in schools, and absence of lab safety equipment for first aid in case of accidents.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine the availability and utilization of instructional materials for implementation of the chemistry curriculum in secondary schools in North Central Nigeria. Specifically the objectives of the study were to;

- i. examine the availability of instructional materials for implementation of Chemistry Curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria;
- ii. find out the difference in the availability of instructional materials for implementation of Chemistry Curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools on the basis of school location in North Central Nigeria;
- iii. find out the difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials for implementation of Chemistry Curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools on the basis of gender in North Central Nigeria;
- iv. find out the difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials for implementation of Chemistry Curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools on the basis of school location in North Central Nigeria;

Research Questions

1. What is the availability of instructional materials for implementation of Chemistry Curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria?
2. What is the difference in the availability of instructional materials for implementation of Chemistry Curriculum between urban and rural Senior Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria?
3. What is the difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials by male and female Chemistry teachers for implementation of Chemistry Curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria?
4. What is the difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials by urban and rural Chemistry teachers for implementation of Chemistry Curriculum in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria?

Hypothesis

Ho1: There is no significant difference in the availability of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by Chemistry teachers in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by male and female Chemistry teachers in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central, Nigeria

Ho3: There is no significant difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by male and female Chemistry teachers in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central, Nigeria.

Ho4: There is no significant difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by urban and rural Chemistry teachers in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central, Nigeria.

METHODOLOGY

The research design was a descriptive survey. Descriptive survey according to Nworgu (2015), is one in which a researcher gathers information about the characteristics of population and analyzing data from the group through the use of questionnaire and interview for finding from the entire population.

The population of the study was Two thousand and forty-eight (2,048) Chemistry teachers in public Senior Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria. The six states of the North Central Zone are Benue, Kogi, Kwara, Nasarawa, Niger and Plateau, including FCT. The sample size of Two hundred and sixty-four (264) Chemistry teachers formed the sample of the study. Multi stage sampling technique was adopted in selecting the sample size. A simple random technique was used in selecting the three state which are Benue, Nasarawa and Niger States. The instrument used for data collection was designed by the

researchers titled Availability and Utilization of Instructional Materials Checklist. The instrument was divided into section A and B. Section A sought information on the personal data of the respondents, while section B contained list of instructional materials for teaching and learning chemistry. The validity was carried out by three experts from the Science and Environmental Education, University of Abuja. The face and content validity were done using the research objectives, question and hypothesis. The reliability was determined by internal consistency method and Cronbach Alpha statistics which gave a reliability coefficient of 0.82 and this indicate the high reliability of the instrument.

Data was collected by distributing the instrument to all the Chemistry teachers in all the visited Schools in both Urban and Rural areas. The letter of introduction from the Head of Department was initially given to Administrators to their seek approval before distributing the questionnaire. The personal data was analyzed using frequency and simple percentage, the research questions were analyzed by mean and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using t-test. The decision rule for research question was if the overall mean is 2.50 and above then the questionnaire items was considered positive and if it is below 2.50 the questionnaire item was considered negative. For null hypotheses, if the P- value was greater than or equals 0.05 level of significance the null hypotheses was rejected; there was no significant difference between the variables, while if the P-value was less than 0.05 level of significance null hypotheses was accepted or retained; there is significant difference between the variable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mean and Standard Deviation on availability of instructional materials for implementation of Chemistry Curriculum N=264

S/N	Instructional Resources	Mean	SD	Decision
76.	Textbooks	3.42	0.79	MA
77.	Wall charts	2.95	0.87	MA
78.	Flipped chart	3.02	0.93	MA
79.	Flat Pictures	2.88	0.90	MA
80.	Posters	2.58	0.83	MA
81.	Chalkboard/Whiteboard	3.57	0.57	MA
82.	Flannel Board	2.43	0.80	SA
83.	Slides	2.55	0.90	MA
84.	Computer	2.51	0.94	MA
85.	Audio-visual	2.27	1.06	SA
86.	Periodic tables	2.74	1.04	MA
87.	Online multimedia lesson	2.22	2.08	SA
88.	Pipettes	2.48	1.16	SA
89.	Beakers	2.57	1.14	MA
90.	Bunsen burner	2.63	1.07	MA
91.	Burettes	3.55	0.72	RA
92.	Tripod stand	3.23	0.88	MA
93.	Chemicals	3.36	0.84	MA
4.	Litmus paper	3.53	0.75	RA

95.	Test tube	3.62	0.71	RA
96.	Volumetric Flasks	2.97	1.04	MA
97.	Safety goggles	2.78	0.90	MA
98.	Lab coat	2.78	0.90	MA
99.	Latex gloves	2.66	1.11	MA
100.	Conical flasks	3.50	0.78	RA
101.	Boiling flask	3.13	0.91	MA
102.	Watch glass	3.61	0.72	RA
103.	Crucibles	3.62	0.79	RA
104.	Funnels	3.66	0.67	RA
105.	Tongs and forceps	3.56	0.77	RA
106.	Spatulas and scoopulas	3.60	0.81	RA
	Sectional Mean	2.93	0.84	MA

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the availability of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum based on location Senior Secondary Schools in North Central. This hypothesis was tested using t-test analysis at $\alpha=0.05$, as shown in the table below.

The table of t-test of Availability of Instructional Materials based on Location

Location	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Remark
Urban	156	3.09	0.66	262	0.219	0.827	Significant
Rural	108	3.08	0.56				

Significant at $p < 0.05$ level

The table showed a summary of t-test analysis on the availability of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by urban and rural schools. The result showed a mean of 3.09 and 3.08 for urban and rural teachers with standard deviation of 0.66 and 0.56 respectively and a significant p-value of 0.827 which was greater than 0.05 level of significance so, the fifth null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there was no significant difference on the availability of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by urban and rural Senior Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by male and female Chemistry teachers in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central, Nigeria. This hypothesis was tested using t-test analysis at $\alpha=0.05$, as shown in table below.

The table of t-test on the Level of Utilization of Instructional Materials for the Implementation of Chemistry Curriculum based on Gender

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Remark
Male	121	3.28	0.51	262	-0.187	0.852	Significant
Female	143	3.29	0.60				

Significant at $p < 0.05$ level

The table showed a summary of t-test analysis on the level of utilization of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by male and female Chemistry teachers. The result showed a mean of 3.28 and 3.29 for male and female teachers with a standard deviation of 0.51 and 0.60 respectively and a significant p-value of 0.852 which was greater than 0.05 level of significance so, the sixth hypothesis was accepted. This means that there was no significant difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by male and female Chemistry teachers in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by urban and rural Chemistry teachers in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central, Nigeria. This hypothesis was tested using t-test analysis at $\alpha=0.05$, as shown in the Table below.

Table of t-test on the Level of availability of instructional materials based on Location

Location	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	P-value	Remark
Urban	156	3.29	0.57	262	11.622	0.00	Significant
Rural	108	2.00	1.21				

Significant at $p < 0.05$ level

The table showed a summary of t-test analysis on the level of utilization of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by urban and rural schools. The result showed a mean of 3.29 and 2.00 for urban and rural schools with a standard deviation of 0.57 and 1.21 respectively and a significant p-value of 0.00 which was less than 0.05 level of significance so, the seventh hypothesis was rejected. This means that there was significant difference in the level of utilization of instructional materials for the implementation of Chemistry Curriculum by urban and rural Chemistry teachers in Senior Secondary Schools in North Central Nigeria.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The study revealed that instructional materials for Chemistry Curriculum implementation are moderately available, with urban teachers having slightly better access. This finding is supported by Uche and Onuoha (2021), who emphasized that urban schools generally receive more funding and have better access to laboratory resources. Similarly, Adebayo (2019) found that rural schools often struggle with inadequate instructional materials, limiting the effectiveness of science instruction.

However, Musa (2018) provided a counterargument, stating that recent educational reforms in Nigeria have increased instructional material distribution to rural areas, reducing disparities. Similarly, Adekunle and Bassey (2018) found that some rural schools, particularly those benefiting from non-governmental organization (NGO) interventions, have instructional materials that rival those of urban schools.

There is high level of improvisation and borrowing of instructional materials and Laboratory equipment in our Senior Secondary Schools. We normally visit about three to four schools to borrow items before carrying out ordinary Titration and if this is happening in Urban Schools, we can imagine what the Rural Schools will look like in terms of instructional materials.

CONCLUSION

Based on the above findings, it was revealed that there was no significant difference in the availability and utilization of instructional materials used in teaching and learning Chemistry among the Chemistry teachers.

RECOMMENDATION

1. The school administrators and teachers should be part of planning of all Senior Secondary School Curriculum for effective planning and implementation. They are the tools for the implementation, so they should be part of the process.

2. Female teachers of Chemistry should be motivated through sponsorship to attend workshops and seminars to enhance the utilization of instructional materials for the Curriculum implementation at the Secondary schools.
3. Government should made funds available for the procurement of instructional materials and a conducive learning environment for teaching and learning of sciences.

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